

**The mass-charge binding energy as an explanation for the superfine adjustment of the
hadron and baryon masses**

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Abstract

Quantum chromodynamics (QCD) describes how mass is created at the quark level. This mechanism is special because the binding of quarks does not result in a mass loss or a release of energy, as in the case of the nuclear mass defect. Rather, mass is created by the binding of quarks. To achieve this binding, energy must be expended. At the same time, however, quarks are firmly bound to each other. Several authors have shown that the masses of the elementary particles as determined by means of QCD agree quite well with the experimentally determined values. In the following, superfine adjustment of the masses of the charged elementary particles is shown to be possible by considering the mass defect in terms of the mass-charge binding energy.

Introduction

The quark model of hadron spectroscopy is crucial for investigating the structures of hadrons and the nature of the interacting forces between their constituents. This model predates quantum chromodynamics (QCD) by several decades and, indeed, led to the development of QCD. Hadrons have been the focus of both experimental and theoretical research since before the development of QCD and will likely continue to be so for decades to come. In the quark model, the gluons of QCD are integrated out and subsumed within the parameters of the strong force. The early quark constituent model has given way to the quark potential model, which attempts to go beyond the global symmetries of the original quark model, being, in essence, a classification based on chiral symmetry breaking, with the dynamics arising from an interquark potential model that has been previously proven successful (1). Simple quarks are genuinely relativistic objects, and their dynamics cannot, in principle, be fully captured by nonrelativistic approximations and leading-order corrections.

QCD is widely accepted as the theory of strong interactions, but no method exists that can be used to solve the QCD *Lagrangian* to achieve a complete understanding of the multitude of observed hadrons and their properties. Other methods, such as lattice QCD calculations, large N_C QCD and effective field theory approaches, appear to be limited in their scope due to their nature yet still offer great promise when used since they afford a detailed understanding of strong interactions (2).

Quantum chromodynamics

According to Carlson, Jaffe, and Wiles (3), QCD is a quantum gauge field theory that describes the strong interactions among colored quarks and gluons, based on group $SU(3)$ of the $SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$ standard model. Following a decade of study, no breakdown of this theory has been confirmed over an enormous energy domain, i.e., $0 < E < 8 \text{ TeV}$. Consequently, QCD is the only known instance of a quantum field theory that can be rigorously defined *nonperturbatively*; hence, it is truly a field theory and not merely an effective field theory (4). In this sense, QCD stands alone as the only internally consistent quantum field theory that is defined at all energy scales.

The *Lagrangian* of QCD is given by

$$L = \sum_q \bar{\varphi}_{q,a} (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu \delta_{ab} - g_s \gamma^\mu t_{ab}^C A_\mu^C - m_q \delta_{ab}) - \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu}^A F^{A\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

where repeated indices are summed over. The γ^μ are the c γ -*matrices*. The $\varphi_{q,a}$ are the quark-field *spinors* for a quark of flavor q and mass m_q , with a color index a that runs from $a = 1$ to $N_c = 3$. The A_μ^C correspond to the gluon fields, with C running from 1 to $N_c^2 - 1 = 8$. They encode the fact that a gluon's interaction with a quark rotates the quark's color in the $SU(3)$ space. The quantity g_s is the QCD coupling constant. Finally, the field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}^A$ is given by

$$F_{\mu\nu}^A = \partial_\mu A_\nu^A - \partial_\nu A_\mu^A - g_s f_{ABC} A_\mu^B A_\nu^C \quad (2)$$

$$[t^A, t^B] = i f_{ABC} t^C \quad (3)$$

Neither quarks nor gluons are observed as free particles. Hadrons are color-singlet combinations of quarks, antiquarks, and gluons. In the framework of *perturbative* QCD (pQCD),

predictions of observables are expressed in terms of the renormalized coupling $\alpha_s(\mu_R^2)$. This coupling satisfies the following renormalization group equation:

$$(\mu_R^2) \frac{d\alpha_s}{d\mu_R^2} = \beta(\alpha_s) = -(b_0\alpha_s^2 + b_1\alpha_s^3 + b_2\alpha_s^4 + \dots) \quad (4)$$

The above framework is used to discuss the electroweak effects in the evolution and determination of QCD coupling (4). The value of this coupling depends on the renormalization scheme in which the coupling is defined.

The quark model

The quark model is also known as the quark potential model. It concerns one or more particles interacting under a given potential. The modeling of quarks began in the 1960s, and corroborating evidence was subsequently discovered (5). This modeling approach provided a reliable basis for the further study of particle physics, yielding results compatible with theoretical predictions. The potential is the most important part of the quark model. Quarks, which are the building blocks of hadrons, are held together by the color force, which is generated by the exchange of gluons, forming color-singlet hadrons. The dynamics underlying this exchange are described by the QCD Lagrangian:

$$\mathcal{L} = i \sum_i \bar{q}_i(x) \left[\partial_\mu - i g_s \sum_a \frac{1}{2} \lambda^a A_\mu^a(x) \right] \gamma^\mu q_i(x) - \frac{1}{4} \sum_a F_{\mu\nu}^a(x) F^{\mu\nu a}(x) - \sum_i \bar{q}_i(x) m_i q_i(x) \quad (5)$$

g_s is the strong coupling constant, and i is defined as the flavor index for $q_i(x)$. λ^a represents 3×3 matrices (Gell-Mann matrices) in which $a = 1, \dots, 8$, and m_i is the mass parameter of the i th quark (6). The strength of the interaction is independent of the flavor. The only flavor dependence arises in the quark-mass terms. To yield finite values for physical quantities, the Lagrangian must be renormalized. Renormalization is a process that renders physical quantities finite and requires the introduction of a dimensional scale parameter μ . A chiral symmetry exists for the QCD Lagrangian in the limit in which the masses of the quarks vanish.

This symmetry can be spontaneously broken through dynamical chiral symmetry breaking. It can also be explicitly broken by the quark masses. Quarks are described as heavy if $m > \Lambda_\chi$ or light if $m < \Lambda_\chi$.

Light quarks and the potential model

The understanding of QCD is strongly founded on the study of light quarks. Approaches involving the application of lattice QCD yield the most accurate and precise values, with the errors encountered being mainly a result of perturbative uncertainties (7). The interactions among baryons and quarks depend weakly on the masses of the quarks involved. These interactions also depend on the electric charges of the particles. The mass difference between the strange and light quarks is very small compared to the scale of confinement. This small difference translates into quite similar properties of baryon states that differ only by an interchange of strange and light quarks (8). The difference in the masses of the up and down quarks is also much smaller than the confinement scale, meaning that the properties of baryon states originating from the interchange of only up and down quarks are also very similar. However, this approach, which is based solely on symmetry, is incapable of explaining certain properties, such as the signs of the $\Sigma - \Lambda$ and $\Delta - N$ splittings (9). Following the development of QCD, novel models based on one-gluon exchanges (OGEs). These include the nonrelativistic potential model and the MIT bag models. The potential model was proposed to calculate radiative transitions and spectra. This model is defined by the Cornell potential, as given in (7):

$$V(r) = -\frac{a}{b} + br + c \quad (6)$$

where the values of the variables a , b and c are extracted from experimental data.

Determination of the QCD parameters

QCD operates in two extreme regimes: the high-energy regime, in which the energies are much higher than that of a typical strong interaction, and the low-energy regime, in which the energies are very small compared to that of a typical strong interaction (10,11). QCD can be used to determine the properties of the quarks, including their masses and α_s . As fundamental parameters, these quantities require both theoretical and experimental confirmation. Since only the masses of hadrons that contain quarks and gluons are considered in experiments, these parameters cannot be determined directly. Instead, they are determined from a collection of relations of the form (11)

$$[M_{HAD}(\Lambda_{QCD}, m_q)]^{TH} = [M_{HAD}]^{EXP} \quad (7)$$

One such relation is required to determine Λ_{QCD} , the running coupling constant and the parameter that fixes $\alpha_s(Q^2)$. α_s denotes the masses of the quarks that are dependent on the renormalization scheme. Therefore, care must be taken to ensure that the definitions are consistent. Measurements of the quark masses at different scales yield a direct quantitative verification of asymptotic freedom in QCD. The high-energy measurement of the hadronic width yields $\alpha_s(M_Z) = 0.1197 \pm 0.0028$, and the measurement of the lower energy of the hadronic branching fraction of the τ lepton yields $\alpha_s(M_Z^2) = 0.1197 \pm 0.0016$ (5). α_s values extracted from different systems can be combined to obtain a more reliable and precise value. Currently, most individual α_s measurements are dominated by theoretical uncertainties. Lattice QCD yields various evaluations of the quark masses. Some of these evaluations have small errors due to proper handling of the nonperturbative part. Although the method of determining scattering lengths using lattice QCD is still early in its development, the masses of the quarks

have been obtained with controlled systematic uncertainties and high precision. The Flavor Averaging Group has estimated the mass of a strange quark, m_s , as well as the average light quark mass as follows (5):

$$\hat{m} \equiv \frac{1}{2}(m_u + m_d) \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{m} = 3.42 \pm 0.06_{stat} \pm 0.07_{sys} \text{ MEV} \quad (9)$$

$$m_s = 93.8 \pm 0.15_{stat} \pm 1.9_{sys} \text{ MEV} \quad (10)$$

The calculation of separate estimates for the masses of the down and up quarks requires the consideration of isospin effects, which arise from both electromagnetic interactions and strong interactions. Current QCD estimates of the masses of the up and down quarks are based on additional input from phenomenology. The effects due to electromagnetism have also been estimated through the inclusion of a quenched magnetic field. The results reported by other researchers have been obtained through a combination of chiral perturbation theory (ChPT) and the global lattice estimate $\hat{m}$, yielding

$$m_u = 2.16 \pm 0.09_{stat+sys} \pm 0.07_{e.m} \text{ MeV} \quad (11)$$

$$m_d = 4.68 \pm 0.14_{stat+sys} \pm 0.07_{e.m} \text{ MeV} \quad (12)$$

Q , the quark-mass ratio, which is a measure of isospin-breaking effects, is then defined by the following equation.

$$Q^2 = \frac{m_s^2 - \hat{m}^2}{m_d^2 - m_u^2} \quad (13)$$

$$Q = 22.6 \pm 0.7_{stat+sys} \pm 0.6_{e.m} \quad (14)$$

In addition to providing accurate values for the light quarks, QCD has also achieved considerable success in determining the effective couplings of ChPT. Because of the considerably larger value of the mass of the strange quark compared to the masses of the other quarks, the issues of convergence and the accuracy of $SU(3)_L \times SU(3)_R$ ChPT are of critical importance.

The values of the masses of the nonstrange quarks can also be determined from the value of Q given that information regarding the mass of the strange quark and $\hat{m}$ is available. Experiments conducted using $\overline{MS}$ at a scale of $\mu = 2 \text{ GeV}$ have yielded the following values (5):

$$m_s = (93.8 \pm 2.4) \text{ MeV} \quad (15)$$

$$\hat{m} = (3.42 \pm 0.09) \text{ MeV} \quad (16)$$

$$m_u = (2.23 \pm 0.14) \text{ MeV} \quad (17)$$

$$m_d = (4.63 \pm 0.14) \text{ MeV} \quad (18)$$

The consideration of pairwise ratios of the quark masses can alleviate the issues surrounding their renormalization. Implementing a similar scheme and scale yields identical QCD renormalization factors for all quark flavors, leading to the cancellation of these factors in the quark-mass ratios; consequently, these ratios are independent of the particular scale and scheme used. Another advantage is that since these ratios are dimensionless, they suffer less from the effects of uncertainties.

Ground-state hadron masses

Based on the interactions among quarks, the properties of the corresponding baryons depend weakly on the masses of the quarks involved and very weakly on their electric charges (12). The properties of baryon states that differ only by an interchange of light and strange quarks are quite similar because the strange-light quark-mass difference is small compared to the confinement scale. The properties of baryon states that differ only by an interchange of up and down quarks are also very similar because of the small difference between the masses of the up and down quarks (13-16). Moreover, the properties of baryon states should be independent of an arbitrary continuous rotation of each quark's flavor in the u , d and s flavor spaces, leading to the $SU(3)_f$ symmetry (3). Regarding the

Gell – Mann – Okubo mass formula (2016), observations lead to certain mass relations between baryons that differ only by the addition of a strange quark, allowing the parameters M_0 , $m_{u,d}$ and m_s to be eliminated from the assumed masses (4).

$$M_N = M_0 + 3m_{n,d} \quad (19)$$

$$M_A = M_E = M_0 + 2m_{u,d} + m_s \quad (20)$$

$$M_E = M_0 + m_{u,d} + 2m_s \quad (21)$$

An analysis of $JP = 1/2^+$ leads to

$$M_E + \frac{3M_A}{2} = M_N + M_E \quad (22)$$

This form contains only the $SU(3)_f$ singlet and a symmetry-breaking octet term. Using the octet dominance rule and the calculation of some $SU(3)_f$ recoupling constants for $8 \times 8 = 1 + 8' + 8''$, one obtains the following (14):

$$M_N = M_1 - 2M_{8'} + M_{8''} \quad (23)$$

$$M_A = M_1 - M_{8'} - M_{8''} \quad (24)$$

$$M_\varepsilon = M_1 + M_{8'} + M_{8''} \quad (25)$$

$$M_\epsilon = M_1 + M_{8'} - 2M_{8''} \quad (26)$$

These equations yield the desired relation and an analysis of $JP = 3/2^+$. Considering only the quark-mass differences yields the Gell-Mann equal spacing rule:

$$M_{(\varepsilon^*)} - M_{\Delta} = M_{(\epsilon^*)} - M_{(\varepsilon^*)} = M_{\varphi} - M_{(\epsilon^*)} \quad (27)$$

According to Dagdeviren (15), a mass formula for a ground-state baryon can be derived using the matrix elements of a mass operator

$$M = a + bY + c[I(I + 1) - Y^2/4] + dJ(J + 1) \quad (28)$$

which contains the above relations for the $J^P = 1/2^+$ octet and $3/2^+$:

$$M_{\varepsilon^*} - M_\varepsilon = M_\epsilon - M_{\epsilon^*} \quad (29)$$

This equation accounts for the energy differences due to the spins of the states and their flavor structure. The mass relation accounts for both the approximate $SU(3)_f$ and *isospin* sym-

metries of the strong interaction, which can be expressed as a linear combination of the $I = 1$ mass splitting, which should be zero (16).

$$N_1 + \epsilon_1 - \varepsilon_1 = 0 \quad (30)$$

where

$$N_1 = M_P - M_n \quad (31)$$

$$\varepsilon_1 = M_{(\varepsilon+)} - M_{(\varepsilon-)} \quad (32)$$

$$\epsilon_1 = M_{(\epsilon^0)} - M_{(\epsilon-*)} \quad (33)$$

This relation holds within the experimental errors on the determined values of the masses. E. Jenkins and Lebed (17) analyzed the experimental errors in the determination of the masses and other ground-state baryon octets in a $1/N_C$ expansion.

QCD-based dynamic models

A dynamic model is required to explain the signs of the $\Delta - N$ and $\Sigma - \Lambda$ splittings, which cannot be determined via mass formula approaches based solely on symmetry (18). The development of QCD led to models of these splittings based on a *one - gluon* exchange. According to Sinha (19), the nonrelativistic potential model relies on multiples with unknown masses, where the mass formula is derived using the *Fermi - Breit* interaction between colored quarks from an OGE. For ground states, the important interaction is the Fermi contact term, which leads to the *ground - state* baryon masses (20):

$$M = \sum_{i=1}^3 m_i + \frac{2\alpha_s}{3} - \frac{8\pi}{3} \langle \delta^3(r) \rangle \sum_{i<j=1}^3 \frac{S_i \cdot S_j}{m_i m_j} \quad (34)$$

where the m_i are the effective masses of the constituent quarks and, by the exchange symmetry of the ground-state spatial wave functions, $\langle \delta^3(r) \rangle$ is the same for any *vecoordinate* $r_{ij} = r_i - r_j$.

The bag model calculation of DeGrand, Jaffe, Johnson, and Kiskis (21) was explained relativistically and confines the quarks to the interior of a hadron by means of a bag pressure term with a parameter B , which is used to set the scale of the baryon masses. Theberge, Thomas, and Miller (22) described the cloudy bag model, which incorporates chiral invariance by allowing a cloud of pion fields to couple to the confined quarks only at the surface of the MIT bag. Belyaev and Ioffe (23) stated that when the masses of the nucleon, Δ , and the lowest-lying D_{13} resonance are also calculated using the QCD sum rules, this leads to a 10 – 15% overestimation with the parameters used in this approach. Leinweber, Thomas, Tsushima, and Wright (24) examined the corrections to the light baryon masses extrapolated from the pion-induced self-energies implied by ChPT. Shifman, Vainshtein, and Zakharov (25) proposed an approach based on the study of the polarization operator for three-quark currents and obtained analogous sum rules for studying the properties of *mesonic* resonances.

Recent models of excited baryon and meson spectra

Godfrey and Isgur (26) solved the Schrodinger equation in a Hilbert space consisting of dressed valence quarks with a finite spatial extent and masses of 220 MeV for the light quarks and 420 MeV for the strange quark (25). Sharma, Blask, Metsch and Huber (27) showed that the inclusion of spin-independent but momentum-dependent terms in an $O(p^2/m^2)$ reduction of the OGE potential reduces the energy of certain positive-parity excited states and raises that of the P-wave excited states (26). Sartor and Stancu (11) presented a parallel extension of OGE-based models. Carlson, Kogut, and Pandharipande (13) proposed a basis that essentially interpolates between Coulomb and linear potential solutions and contains a factor that decreases as the length of the Y-shaped string connecting the quarks increases.

Hooft (14) calculated an alternate QCD-based candidate for the short-range interactions between quarks, known as *instanton* effects. Shuryak and Rosner (16) introduced a simple model to explore the ground-state baryon mass splitting with *instanton*-induced interactions. Blask, Bohn, Huber, Metsch, and Petry (18) extensively studied meson and baryon spectra using a string-based confining interaction and instanton-induced interactions. Evidence for the role of *instantons* in determining the light-hadron structure and quark propagation in a QCD vacuum was given by Chu, Grandy, Huang, and Negele (20) in a study based on lattice QCD.

Glozman and Riska (22) popularized this idea by performing an extensive analysis of the baryon spectrum using a model based on a hyperfine interaction arising solely from the exchange of a pseudoscalar octet. Glozman, Plessas, Varga, and Wagenbrunn (24) extended this model to include the exchange of vector mesons and a scalar meson and the calculation of radial matrix elements of the exchange potentials.

The calculations performed to date show that the sum rule method using basic and necessary concepts of QCD is completely applicable for considerations regarding baryons and mesons, and hence, this method has been successfully accepted. In practical terms, however, the models for neither the baryon spectrum nor the meson spectrum are relativistic, nor is QCD, and although some aspects reflect certainty regarding the masses and properties of excited baryons and mesons, the spin-orbit puzzle for baryons is still a topic of active research. It is obvious that a solution will ultimately require a description of the baryons in a relativistic framework.

Meson and baryon masses and the mass-charge binding energy

A rough explanation of the masses of the mesons and baryons is best enabled by QCD.

However, the mass-charge binding energy is responsible for the superfine structure of the meson and baryon masses.

To recognize this, one must understand exactly how the mass-charge binding energy is calculated at the level of the elementary particles. To do so, one first sums the net charges without considering their signs. This net charge sum is then multiplied by the mass of the elementary particle.

The resulting mass-charge binding energy is then released. This release of the mass-charge binding energy reduces the energy and, thus, the mass of the elementary particle. The masses of the various elementary particles therefore decrease as their net charges $\sum|bq_j|$ increase.

$$z = (bq, m) = bq + mi \quad \text{with} \quad b = \text{const} \quad (35)$$

$$F_{z,z} = G \frac{z_1 z_2}{r^2} = G \frac{(bq_1 + m_1 i)(bq_2 + m_2 i)}{r^2} \quad (36)$$

$$\text{z-z energy } E_{z,z} = -G \frac{z_1 z_2}{r} = G \frac{(bq_1 + m_1 i)(bq_2 + m_2 i)}{r} \quad (37)$$

$$\text{mass-charge energy } E_{m,q} = -G \frac{\sum|bq_j| \times mi}{r} = G \sum|bq_j| \times \left(\frac{mi}{r}\right) \quad (38)$$

$$\text{with } \left(\frac{m_i}{r}\right) \approx \text{const} \Rightarrow E_{m,q} \approx G \sum |bq_j| \times \text{const.} \quad (39)$$

It is theorized that the radii of the baryons increase almost proportionally to their energy content, at least for baryon oscillations, implying that $m \sim r$; see, e.g., ref. (28).

If for higher energy states of baryon oscillations, the baryon energy content is increasing, and if the baryon radius is simultaneously increasing, then the mass-charge energy effect should correspondingly decrease, resulting in a unification of different baryon entities in terms of their masses for higher oscillation states.

The B mesons exhibit a special feature. For B mesons, the observed difference in the masses of the charged and uncharged B mesons is surprisingly very small. Due to the large masses of the B mesons, however, the mass difference should be very large. This discrepancy can be explained if the B mesons are larger and have a greater radius than expected. Given the large masses of the B mesons, one would expect them to have very small radii. However, the experimentally determined radii of the B mesons are, also surprisingly, very large. This observation can explain the small difference in the masses of the charged and uncharged B mesons. The reactions of the elementary particles can also be well explained and understood by considering the mass-charge binding energy. While it seems possible to produce a charge without any limitations, the mass is strictly limited. Mass (or energy) is subject to a conservation law, whereas net charge is not subject to any conservation law as long as positive and negative charges are produced in equal amounts, i.e., the absolute sum of the positive and negative charges produced is always zero. Consequently, the amount of energy released can be maximized by maximizing the mass-charge binding energy through the unlimited production of a net charge, as long as positive and negative charges are produced in equal parts. Thus, bulky elementary particles can decay into smaller elementary particles, which acquire net charges. In this way, the mass-charge binding energy is maximized.

Table 1 gives the net charges and masses as well as the mass differences between the charged and uncharged particles for some exemplary baryons.

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Table 1. The masses of baryons

Baryons	$I(J^P)$	Full quark formula	Basic formula	Net charge	Observed mass	Difference
<u>n and p</u>						
n	$1/2(1/2^+)$	udd	SSS	4/3	939.57	
p	$1/2(1/2^+)$	uud	SSS-3e	5/3	938.27	1.3
<u>uds, uus, dds</u>						
Σ^+	$1(1/2^+)$	u'u's4	P4	5/3	1189.4	
Σ^0	$1(1/2^+)$	u'd's4	P4-	4/3	1192.6	3.2
Σ^-	$1(1/2^+)$	d'd's4	N4-	3/3	1197.4	4.8
Σ^+	$1(3/2^+)$	u'u's7	P7	5/3	1382.8	
Σ^0	$1(3/2^+)$	u'd's7	P7-	4/3	1383.7	4.4
Σ^-	$1(3/2^+)$	d'd's7	N7-	3/3	1387.2	3.5
<u>uss, dss</u>						
Ξ^0	$1/2(1/2^+)$	u'ss	NS1	4/3	1314.9	
Ξ^-	$1/2(1/2^+)$	d'ss	NS1-	3/3	1321.3	6.4
Ξ^0	$1/2(3/2^+)$	u'ss4	N9+-	4/3	1531.8	
Ξ^-	$1/2(3/2^+)$	d'ss4	N10-	3/3	1535.0	3.2
<u>usc, dsc</u>						
Ξ_c^+	$1/2(1/2^+)$	u'sc1	NS ₃ 8+	5/3	2465.6	
Ξ_c^{0c}	$1/2(1/2^+)$	d'sc1	N S ₃ 8+-	4/3	2470.3	4.7
<u>bottom</u>						
Ξ^0_b		usb		4/3	5787.8	
Ξ^-_b		dsb		3/3	5791.1	3.3